

EFFECT OF SOCIAL MEDIA COMMUNICATION ON SELECT TOURIST SITES IN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT— This researched work is on the effect of social media communication on select tourist sites in Nigeria. Social media enables people to share the most significant memories from their travels with a vast audience. Social media is a computer-based technology that facilitates the sharing of ideas, thoughts, and information through the building of virtual network. Tourist sites are places people visit for its inherent nature usually when they are on vacation. The Problem of study was identified by a researcher who posits that social media communication helps organizations to reach their customers and potential customers. The general objective investigated the effects of social media communications on select tourist sites in Nigeria. This study will be of immense benefit to Future researchers, Upcoming generation and Tourist sites across the world. This research equally was achieved through primary data, later analysed with SPSS statistical package. However, simple linear regression was employed and findings revealed that the correction coefficient are very high as against the p-value. This depicts that social media communications (WhatsApp and Facebook) affects tourist sites highly in the select tourist sites leading to the rejection of the two null hypotheses. Concluding that social media communications WhatsApp and Facebook are significant on tourist sites in Nigeria. The researcher recommends that tourist sites and indeed all other organizations who wish to remain in the business should endeavor to communicate with their customers and potential customers through Facebook and WhatsApp More as More people are in the use of both communications now than before.

Keywords—*social media, Facebook, WhatsApp, tourist and tourist sites.*

I. INTRODUCTION

social media according to Chung and buhalis(2008) is defined as a virtual communications which involves the use of WhatsApp, Facebook and other means to persuade or communicate an offering by a particular organization to its customers and intended customers for the purpose of enhanced patronage. Tourism means traveling out of ones place of residence for the purpose of leisure, business etc. A tourist is one who travels out of his or her usual place of residence for the purpose of education, pleasure and relaxation and staying in that destination for not less than one year and not More than one consecutive year at a particular time interval. Tourist sites are places people visit for its aesthetic beauty during their pleasure time (De-krishna 2008). This research study verified the effect of social media communications with focus on Facebook and WhatsApp on select tourist sites in Nigeria.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

SOCIAL MEDIA: Dulcic (2005) is of the view that Internet provides a capability so powerful and general that it can be

used for almost any purpose that depends on information, and it is accessible by every individual who connects to one of its constituent networks. Farrokkh (2009) opines that It supports human communication via social media, electronic mail (e-mail), “chat rooms,” newsgroups, and audio and video transmission and allows people to work collaboratively at many different locations. It supports access to digital information by many applications, including the World Wide Web. The Internet has proved to be a spawning ground for a large and growing number of “e-businesses” (including subsidiaries of traditional “brick-and-mortar” companies) that carry out most of their sales and services over the Internet Fotis,(Buhalis and Rossides 2012). Gate (2019) in his view posits that the dissemination of digitized text, pictures, and audio and video recordings over the Internet, primarily available today through the World Wide Web, has resulted in an information explosion. The researcher further said that Clearly, powerful tools are needed to manage network-based information and Information available on the Internet today may not be available tomorrow without careful attention’s being paid to preservation and archiving techniques. The key

to making information persistently available is infrastructure and the management of that infrastructure (Kent 1994). He further posits that At first these repositories may be dominated by digital objects specifically created and formatted for the World Wide Web. He further said that Movement of digital objects from one repository to another will still leave them available to users who are authorized to access them, while replicated instances of objects in multiple repositories will provide alternatives to users who are better able to interact with certain parts of the Internet than with others. Information will have its own identity and, indeed, become a “first-class citizen” on the Internet (kinwar 2002).

According to Michael(2017) the tourism and Hospitality Industry has been one of the earliest industries using social media Communication to promote their products and services. Wimmer and Dominic(2017) is of the opinion also that Internet plays a big role since it has been discovered in every corner of the world. However Morrison, Rimmington and Williams(2019) posit that internet connection is a wide communication network, tourism site's can make a direct relation with the public using it. Product distribution and services of agencies cannot depend on quantity of printed papers anymore and information about them can reach millions of the internet users. Let's consider some of the advantages of using social media communications in Tourism industry as gathered by (Tunde 2012) below.

1. In the modern world travel agencies can use internet as a profitable medium of tourism promotion and sales.
2. Good quality of promotional visualization of tourism services and products through internet can create a better impression in the people than brochures and catalogues.
3. The internet represents an efficient and useful distribution channel for collecting clients and it helps to identify their desires.

4. Internet allows the improvement of efficiency of travel agencies by speeding up communication and providing all the necessary information.
5. Contemporary business in tourism market is characterized by the implementation of various booking systems in to business systems of travel agencies, hotel chains, airlines etc.
6. The internet allows high quality and effective market research and industrial espionage.

ADVANTAGES OF THE SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE IN CONDUCTING BUSINESS IN TOURISM INDUSTRIES as compiled by (Raza 2006) below.

1. In contemporary travel agencies and tour operator's business, the Internet has shown to be a profitable medium of tourism promotion and sales.
2. 'The Internet represents an interesting and useful distribution channel for collecting clients and it provides the ability to identify their desires.' (Čavlek,, 2000).
3. Promotional visualization of tourism services and products through multimedia technology leaves greater impression on potential customer than standard brochures, catalogues and leaflets.
4. Overbooking has become almost impossible because all communication problems that may cause it are removed.
5. The Internet allows the improvement of travel agencies and tour operators by speeding up communication and providing all the necessary information.
2. Product distribution and services of agencies do not depend on the quantity of printed catalogues anymore and information about them can reach millions of the Internet users.

3. The Internet provides selling services of travel agencies on demand.
4. CRS/GDS systems allow better and more efficient business with clients to contemporary travel agencies.

‘Greater added values which agencies, by using the Internet, can provide to clients high-quality information, quick offer of services related to travel, fast order, express delivery and human personality.’ (Ruelcke, 2000).

2.3 SOCIAL MEDIA

Oguntude and Oyeyipo (2012) is of the opinion that Social media is a computer-based technology that facilitates the sharing of ideas, thoughts, and information through the building of virtual networks. By design, social media is Internet-based and gives users quick electronic communication of content. Content includes personal information, documents, videos, and photos. Users engage with social media via a computer, tablet, or smartphone via web-based software or applications.

Social media originated as a way to interact with friends and family but was later adopted by businesses that wanted to take advantage of a popular new communication method to reach out to customers. However in this study the reseacher considered the power of social media as the ability to connect and share information with anyone on Earth, or with many people simultaneously.

2.3. TYPES OF SOCIAL MEDIA as put in place by Ogunberu(2011) is summarized as Social media may take the form of a variety of tech-enabled activities. These activities include photo sharing, blogging, social gaming, social networks, video sharing, business networks, virtual worlds, reviews, and much more.

Even governments and politicians utilize social media to engage with constituents and voters.

In the same vain Nyheim,Fadden and Connolly(2005) suggested that For individuals, social media is used to keep in touch with friends and extended family. Some people will use various social media applications to network career opportunities, find people across the globe with like-minded interests, and share their thoughts, feelings, insights, and emotions. Those who engage in these activities are part of a virtual social network. For businesses, social media is an indispensable tool and organizations use the platform to find and engage with customers, drive sales through advertising and promotion, inbgaue consumer trends, and offering customer service or support. Social media Come in form of Facebook,YouTube,WhatsApp, Instagram,Tiktok,QQ,DouyinSino Weibo etc.

2.3 BENEFITS OF SOCIAL MEDIA

According to koelzer and Cox(2015) Social media has changed the way that we all interact with each other online. It's gives us the ability to discover what's happening in the world in real-time, to connect with each other and stay in touch with long-distance friends, and in order to have access to endless amounts of information at your fingertips. In many senses, social media has helped many individuals find common ground with others online, making the world seem more approachable. The use of social media is correlated with having more friends and more diverse personal networks, especially within emerging economies.For many teenagers, friendships can start virtually, with 57% of teens having met a friend online. Kotler (2014) in his opinion suggested that Businesses are also using social media marketing to target their consumers right on their phones and computers, building a following in order to build a loyal fan or customers.

2.4 TOURISM

Tourism, the act and process of spending time away from home in pursuit of recreation, relaxation, and pleasure Kalaketa(2012).

Tourism has become one of the major players in international commerce, and represents at the same time one of the main income sources for many developing countries. This growth goes hand in hand with an increasing diversification and competition among destinations. This global spread of tourism in industrialized and developed states has produced economic and employment benefits in many related sectors - from construction to agriculture or telecommunication. Tourism as the totality of the relationship and phenomenon arising from the travel and stay of strangers provided the stay does not imply the establishment of a permanent residence and is not connected with a remunerated activity (Tunde, 2012). World Tourism Organization (WTO 2017) defines it as an activity involving the travels of persons to places outside their usual environment for not more than one year and not less than twenty four hours for leisure, business, rest and education purposes.

1) 2.4. Types of Tourism Activities

Tunde, (2012) analyzed various types of tourism structure as follows:

1. **Ethnic Tourism:** This is travelling for the purpose of observing the cultural expressions and life-styles of truly exotic people. Examples include visits to native homes, attending dances and ceremonies and possibly participating in religious rituals.
2. **Cultural Tourism:** This type of tourism involves having experience and, in

some cases, participates in a vanishing lifestyle that lies within human memory e.g. costume festivals, folk performances, arts and crafts etc.

3. **Historical Tourism:**

Travelling to places where there are museum, cathedral circuits that stresses the glories of the past e.g. guided tours of moments.

4. **Environmental Tourism:**

To travel for the purpose of “getting back to nature”, man-land relationships. It is primarily geographic in nature and will include destinations such as Assop waterfalls, Plateau state. Aso rock, Abuja, Rock formation Jos Plateau, Yankari National Park Bauchi and other natural wonders.

5. **Recreational Tourism:** It

includes taking part in sports, sun bathing “Ayo” or Ludo game and social contacts in relaxed environment. 6. **Business Tourism:** This centers on participation in conventions, meetings, seminars and form of travel.

2.6 TOURIST DESTINATION / ATTRACTION

A **tourist** is a person who is visiting a place for pleasure and interest, especially when they are on holiday and who usually spend up to twenty four hours and does not spend more than one consecutive year (Raza 2006).

A **destination** is a geographical area consisting of all the services and infrastructure necessary for the stay of a specific tourist. Destinations are therefore an important part of a tourism product (Jones 2019).

A **tourist attraction** is a place of interest where tourists visit, typically for its inherent or an exhibited natural or cultural value, historical significance, natural or built beauty, offering leisure and amusement (Dulcic 2005).

2.6 IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON TOURISM DESTINATION

The appearance of the social media and the incredibly rapid development of highly sophisticated computer and telecommunication technology have made the world a global village. 'Communication network satellites provide the quickest and the cheapest data transfer to all parts of the world, a great agreement among thousands of computer systems that communicate with each other is represented by the Internet.' (Kent, 1994). The Development of information technology and the creation of computer networks and the Internet have enabled a new way of communication which has helped many organizations and destination to communicate her offering through the use of social media platforms. However Gates (2019) confirmed that social media has helped many hotel in Lagos State to communicate her offering faster than before. The internet provides a better access to numerous sources of information around the world, as well as direct communication with all users. 'The Internet is a collection of computer networks around the world and as such is the largest computer system that millions of computer users can use and share all kinds of information including tourism destinations. (Gates 1999). The Internet has become a support to more complex and critical functions in tourism and hospitality industry and it contributed to its significant innovation.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research study focused on the effect of social media communication with reference to Facebook and WhatsApp on select tourist sites in Nigeria. The researcher limited his research work on select tourist sites in Nigeria which includes Obudu Mountain Resort, Kainji national park, Rojenny tourist Village, Marina resort, Lekki conservation centre, Eleko Beach, Akwa Wonderland, and Ikwe Holiday Resort. However, the choice of choosing these organisations was based on Popularity and they are doing well according N.T.D.C. yearly Buletin. The researcher also concentrated on only those staff who occupies the position of managers, senior staff and supervisors and the reason was because they are the people who are involved in management decision more than the lower ranked. Population of staff was retrieved at different organizations administrative units. The questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents, the Taro Yamane (1967) formula was used to determine the sampled population. It is calculated below: However, the population of study was 329 staff, put together. See Table 3.1 below.

TOURIST SITES	SUPERVISOR SENIOR STAFF AND MANAGERS	OTHERS	TOTAL
Obudu Mountain Resort (O.M.R)	50	150	200
Kainji National Part (K.N.P)	60	90	150
Rejenny Tourist Village (R.T.V)	21	44	65
Marina Resort (M.R)	48	54	102
Lekki Conservation Centre (L.C.C)	72	88	160
Eleko Beach (E.B)	32	50	82
Awaka Wonderland (A. W. L)	20	30	50
Ikwe Holiday Resort (I.H.R)	26	56	80
Total	329	562	889

Table 3.1

Source: Field survey, 2018

$$(n) \cong N/1 + N (e)^2$$

$$L.C.C (n) = N/1 + N (e)^2$$

$$n = 329/1 + 329 (0.058)^2$$

$$n = 329/1 + 329 (0.003364)$$

$$n = 329 (1+1.106756)$$

$$n = 329/1. 106756$$

$$n = 297.2 \cong 297 \text{ staff}$$

The researcher however, concludes to concentrate on the total population, since the differences are not

much and numbers of staff are not large enough. The data was analysed using S.P.SS and simple linear regression analysis.

4.1 Data Analysis and Results

Research Question One

What is the extent of the effect of Facebook communication on tourist sites?

Hypothesis One

H₀: facebook communication does not have a significant effect on tourist site's.

Table 4.1: Output of Analyses Concerning Research Question One

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics
1	.556 ^a	.309	.307	.408	.309

	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.309	142.530	1	319	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), FSM

Table 4.1.1: Output of Analyses Concerning Hypothesis One

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.302	.130		10.000	.000
	DIS	.189	.016	.556	11.939	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TOS

Table 4.1 shows the result obtained in respect of research question one, while Table 4.1.1 shows the result obtained in respect of hypothesis one. The result reveals that the correlation coefficient is 0.556, which is moderate. This implies that Facebook communications has a significant effect on tourist site's and it affects tourist site's moderately. Furthermore,

Table 4.1.1 displays that the p-value for Facebook communications is 0.000, which is less than the level of significance (0.05), hence leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis, concluding that Facebook as a social media communication are significant on tourist site's.

Research Question Two

What extent does WhatsApp social media communications affect tourist site's?

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: This is no significant effect between whatsapp social media communications and tourist sites.

Table 4.2: Output of Analysis Concerning Research Question two

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.559 ^a	.312	.310	1.041	.312	144.768	1	3	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), WSM

Table 4.2.1: Output of Analyses Concerning Hypothesis Two

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	18.395	.332		55.412	.000
	DIS	.485	.040	.559	12.032	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TOS

Table 4.2 shows the result obtained in respect of research question two, while Table 4.2.1 shows the result obtained in respect of hypothesis two. The result reveals that the correlation coefficient is 0.559, which is moderate. This implies that the usage of WhatsApp

communications affect tourist site's moderately. Furthermore, Table 4.2.1 displays that the p-value for whatsapp is 0.000, which is less than the level of significance (0.05), hence leading to the rejection of the

null hypothesis, concluding that WhatsApp usage by tourist sites positively affects them.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

The result in respect of research question one reveals that the correlation coefficient is 0.556, which is high. This implies that Facebook usage by tourist site's affects them highly in the selected tourist sites. Furthermore, the result reveals that the p-value for Facebook social media communications is 0.000, which is less than the level of significance (0.05), hence leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis, concluding that Facebook social media communications usage by tourist site's are significant on tourist sites existence in the select tourist sites. The result of this study is in line with the findings of Mamaghani (2009) whose result revealed that progressive liberalization of global markets are likely to result in increased competitiveness and effective increased usage of social media communications in the regional sugar industry as firms seek to grow their capabilities in order to trade globally. The result of this study also agrees with the result of Farrokh (2009) whose findings revealed that social media communications usages has significant impact on project ability indices, the result of the analysis are quite compelling by indicating strong support for the matching of Facebook on profitability indices and performance implications of the match between social media communications and financial (Performance indices are significantly higher in matched strategy types, it means special pair wise strategy types indicating higher range of profitability in the organization or firm. The result of this study agrees with the findings of Chung and Buhalis (2008) whose result revealed that the success of consumer products largely depends on the social media communications. Distribution as an element of marketing mix brings the products to market, intensifies the demand for existing products and provides better position of the company on the market and others.

The result of research question two reveals that the correlation coefficient is 0.559, which is very high. This implies that whatsapp social media communications affect tourist site's very high. Furthermore, the p-value for social media communications is 0.000, which is less than the level of significance (0.05), hence leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis, concluding that whatsapp social media communications usages by tourist sites positively affects the select tourist sites. The result of this study is in line with the findings of Obasan, Michael (2017) whose result revealed that indeed market distribution requires social media communications and product market performance of the observed firms and of all the factors considered social media communications strategy were found to be most important for efficient market performance. The result is also in agreement with the result of Morrison, Rimmington and Williams (2019) whose result revealed that a detailed and well organized distribution strategy contributes to the efficient market performance and brand image it also lead to low costs, higher sales and higher efficiency thereby leading to higher profits to the firm. They equally found that the companies who are performing better in the countries actually formulated the following distribution route. Lastly the result of this study agrees with the study of Kinwar (2002) whose result revealed that distribution strategy must involved whatsapp social media communications as it helps the organization in performance level such as brand image, and that distribution enables the producer's product and services to get to the customers at the right time since many people are now using whatsapp social media communications.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS & RESULTS

This research focused at investigating the effect of social media communications on select tourist site's in Nigeria. The objectives of the research are to examine the effect of Facebook social media communications on tourist sites and to examine the effect of whatsapp usages of tourist site's on tourist site's. The methodology employed the simple linear regression analysis since it enabled the researcher to capture the essence of the work effectively in addition to its high level of simplicity and global acceptability. The empirical analysis carried out in this study reveals that social media communications usages of tourist sites affects the organization highly in selected tourist sites and whatsapp usages of the tourist site are significant on organizational existence in selected tourist sites. Again, whatsapp social media communications of tourist site's affect the organizations very high, and whatsapp usages of tourist sites positively affects select tourist sites in Nigeria.

V. CONCLUSION

Tourism industry are where multifaceted activities are taking place. And the selected tourist sites are overwhelmingly contributing their quota and with a bold vision of becoming a preferred choice of destination across Nigeria and Africa. In its effort towards achieving this vision, they have made progress in acquiring a large customers/tourists. However, this growth has been as a result of their persistent use of social media communications which has brought it increased market demand.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The researcher recommend as follows:

Since it has been discovered and confirmed in this research that Facebook social media communications affect tourists sites highly in there business, any organization/tourist sites who wish to keep growing in the business should embrace Facebook social media communications so as to be a preferred choice of destination and this will help them towards rewarding her stakeholders adequately.

Secondly, since it was also revealed that whatsapp social media communications of the selected tourist site usually affect the

organizations highly. The reseacher however recommend that organizations/tourist sites should always adopt and implement the use of whatsapp social media communications if they wish to be known by the majority of their customers which will help in positioning them above other's.

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